

INCREASE THE OPERATION OF EXCAVATORS OF THE FOURTH SIZE GROUP**Nikita Medvedev,***Master's degree student**Kharkiv National Automobile and Highway University***Igor Pimonov***Candidate of Technical Sciences, Head of the Department of Operation,**Testing, Service of Construction and Road Machines**Kharkiv National Automobile and Road University***Abstract**

The fleet of road construction machines (RCMs) currently consists of tens of thousands of machines. Maintaining this fleet of machines in good working order requires huge costs. Currently, a large number of employees are engaged in repairing road construction machines. The metal consumption over the full service life of a machine is close to its weight, and the cost of all measures to keep the machine in working order over the same period is 8-15 times higher than the cost of the machine itself.

The construction of new roads and reconstruction of existing ones in Ukraine is a large-scale economic task that is essential for the country's further development. The plan is to build and reconstruct paved motorways. Improving the reliability of construction and road machines and reducing their maintenance costs is a national priority.

One of the most expensive components of construction and road machines is the hydraulic drive. Due to a number of advantages, the hydraulic drive has been widely used in various construction and road construction machines in recent years. Depending on the complexity of the machine, the hydraulic drive accounts for between thirty and eighty per cent of all failures. Therefore, ensuring the reliability of the hydraulic drive ensures the reliability of the entire machine and increases the efficiency of the entire construction organization.

Keywords: working fluids, hydraulic drive, filtering, excavator, operation.

The aim of the work is to ensure the efficiency of the excavator by improving it:

- the quality of cleaning the working fluid from contaminants, including air and water;
- indicators of pressure (power) loss for cleaning the working fluid;
- power supply to the pump.

To achieve this goal, the thesis project considers, develops and improves the on-board oil cleaning system and the ejector pump power supply as a single system using design ideas patented by the inventors.

The use of the developed filter unit results in pressure losses that do not exceed those of the best domestic and foreign filter designs. At the same time, the quality of purification is ensured.

The main components of the oil cleaning unit are either available as a series or contain mostly standard parts.

The advantage of volumetric fluid flow dividers is that there is virtually no pressure loss, which is an important advantage compared to throttle dividers, which lose pressure during operation. Therefore, it is advisable to use volumetric flow dividers in the hydraulic drive of an excavator. Typically, flow dividers are used to synchronise the speed of several hydraulic motors (power cylinders or hydraulic motors) powered by a single (common) pump. In this case, synchronisation of several units means ensuring both equality and ratio of the speed of the hydraulic motors.

It should be noted that the quality indicators of working fluids, reaching their limit value, determine its failure. Failure is understood as a technical condition of the working fluid in which it completely or partially

loses its efficiency and cannot perform the specified functions with the established parameters.

The design of a hydraulic fluid filtration system depends on a number of factors: the size of the installation, the sensitivity of certain types of hydraulic equipment to contamination, the required degree of operational reliability, the type of fluid, and, finally, the operating conditions.

For small hydraulic actuators (with a pump with a flow rate of 35 l/min) operating intermittently at a pressure not exceeding 63-100 kgf/cm², it is sufficient to install one filter in the suction line. In most cases, a strainer with a mesh size of 100-200 microns is sufficient to prevent contaminants dangerous to the normal operation of the hydraulic actuator from entering the hydraulic system. For medium-sized hydraulic actuators (with a pump with a flow rate of 200 l/min) operating at pressures up to 200 kg/cm² (20 MPa) and with longer pipelines, a filter must be installed in the suction line in addition to the suction line filter. For large hydraulic drives with a reservoir capacity of more than 1000-2000 litres (large presses, rolling mills, etc.), an independent filtering system for the working fluid must be provided. In these cases, it is also advisable to install special sump tanks into which the oil from the hydraulic system is drained. The sump tanks must be of sufficient size, otherwise contaminants will not settle and will be reintroduced into the system. Filter the fluids at regular intervals. Fill and air filters should also be provided in every hydraulic system.

Careful consideration must be given to the selection of the suction filter, as the suction vacuum must not exceed a certain value during the entire period of

pump operation. If the suction vacuum exceeds the permissible value, it is necessary to increase the diameter of the suction pipe and reduce the flow rate of the working fluid through the filter by reducing the pump flow rate (in an adjustable pump, the maximum flow rate is limited by a control mechanism, in an unregulated pump, by reducing the rotation speed or using a pump with a lower flow rate); install a filter element with a higher capacity; reduce the suction height of the pump; install a filter with a higher capacity or increase the number of filters.

Premature pump failure is caused by cavitation, which in most cases is the result of an improperly selected suction filter. When using expensive high-pressure pumps with high flow rates, it is advisable to use low-cost booster pumps (usually centrifugal) that feed the oil directly into the suction line of the main pump through the filter. In addition to a guaranteed suction head, this ensures finer filtration of the oil entering the main pump. Suction filters are highly efficient. Numerous studies conducted by VNIIGidropivod and foreign companies (e.g., Rosain) have proven that the installation of suction filters with a filter fineness of 74 microns is equivalent in efficiency to the installation of filters on the discharge line with a filter fineness of 25 microns. It is not advisable to install filters with a filtration fineness of less than 74 μm on the suction line.

In automated hydraulic drives with complex operating cycles and expensive control systems, it is necessary to provide for the installation of fine filters in the lines under pressure from the working fluid. The installation of high-pressure fine filters is necessary to protect sensitive hydraulic distribution and control equipment.

The following values of the permissible pressure drop (p) on the filter are recommended: for high-pressure filters with a relief valve, $p = 1.05 \dots 1.4 \text{ kg/cm}^2$; for high-pressure filters without a relief valve, $p = 1.05 \dots 1.8 \text{ kg/cm}^2$; for drain filters, $p = 0.35 \dots 0.70 \text{ kg/cm}^2$. When using metal-ceramic and other similar materials, these values can be increased, but they should not exceed 6 kg/cm^2 . The maximum working

pressure for high-pressure filter housings should not exceed the value determined by the formula

$$P_{\text{max}} = \frac{f p_{\text{br}}}{n}, \quad (1)$$

where p_{max} is the maximum operating pressure for the filter housing, kg/cm^2 ;

p_{br} - breaking pressure for the filter housing, kg/cm^2 ;

f - quality factor ($f = 1$ for casings without welding and castings; $f = 0.8$ for casings with welding or non-cast iron castings; $f = 0.7$ for casings made of cast iron castings);

n is the safety factor ($n = 4$ for pressures of $0-20 \text{ kg/cm}^2$; $n = 3.5$ for pressures of $20-63 \text{ kg/cm}^2$; $n = 3$ for pressures $>63 \text{ kg/cm}^2$).

Construction and road machines are characterized by a large dispersion in the rate of change of the main indicators of the properties of the working fluids used. This is due to the influence of a significant number of design and operational factors on the actual process of changing indicators.

The quality of working fluid purification can be improved by developing an oil purification unit, which is a combined structure consisting of a hydrocyclone, centrifugal filter, magnetic filter, fine filter and flow separator. The use of a flow separator reduces pressure losses, which directly saves machine energy that can be used to perform useful work.

Basically, the oil cleaning unit consists of parts and components whose reliability has been thoroughly tested in operation.

References

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